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Project title (preliminary): **User adherence to mHealth and the role of patient support apps in self-management of diabetes**

Objectives: Patient support apps have risen in popularity and provide new opportunities in self-care of chronic conditions. They transform smart phones into medical tools, offering users an active role in the management of their disease. However, little is known about who uses mHealth and how intensively users engage with it. It is the aim of this study to (i) identify user characteristics that are associated with demand for mHealth, (ii) develop a measure to assess user engagement and investigate how intensively patients use apps for disease management and (iii) assess the quality of mHealth data and its applicability to machine learning (ML) prediction models.

Methods: The analysis is based on real world evidence obtained by Novo Nordisk's Cornerstones4Care® diabetes support app. User engagement was calculated as the number of days with ≥ 1 activity/ the number of possibly active days, and as measures expressing the persistence, longevity and regularity of interaction. Stepwise multivariate regressions were used to assess the associations between user characteristics (e.g. age, gender etc.) and engagement outcomes for each module of the app (e.g. tracking of medication intake, food etc.). We aim to compare different ML algorithms and assess their ability/ power to predict user intensity based on the patient characteristics collected by the app.

Results: 29643 users have registered the application. Users were on average 50 years old. 65% were type 2 diabetes patients and 14% type 1 (21% other). Amongst 6632 users who shared information about their gender, 41% are male. Amongst 6151 users who shared height and weight, mean BMI was 35,15. Amongst those who set up a medication profile, 54% were treated with insulins, thereof 62% with fast-acting bolus insulins, i.e. having a higher need for constant self-monitoring. Blood glucose (BG) monitoring was most widely applied, whereas continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) was the least used module. Preliminary regression results indicate that female users engage more actively with the app (0.07, $p < 0.05$), while results on intensity of use and other factors associated with it are still outstanding.

Discussion: Identification of user profiles may inform design of health apps, help to target intervention programs and encourage adequate self-monitoring. In the next step, our results should be linked to health outcomes in order to assess if and how the intensity of usage influences the users' health. Our study will assess if app data based on real world evidence is sufficient for this purpose. Given the increasing disease prevalence, low healthcare workforce and resource restrictions, it is the ultimate goal to investigate if mHealth is an opportunity to increase quality of care for health care systems.

The poster/ oral presentation will contain the full results of the study, while this abstract contains only preliminary insights.